

CODEN [USA]: IAJPBB

ISSN: 2349-7750

**INDO AMERICAN JOURNAL OF
PHARMACEUTICAL SCIENCES**Available online at: <http://www.iajps.com>

Research Article

**METABOLIC SYNDROME IN PATIENTS WITH ACUTE
ISCHEMIC STROKE**

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Article Received: February 2019 Accepted: March 2019 Published: April 2019

Abstract:

OBJECTIVE: To determine the metabolic syndrome in patients with acute ischemic stroke.

PATIENTS AND METHODS: All patients with stroke age ≥ 35 year of age and either gender presenting with neuroradiological features of stroke (clinically and CT scan proven including major and minor stroke) were recruited and entered in this cross sectional study. Data collected using a pretested proforma meeting the objectives of the study while all the relevant population were explored for metabolic syndrome whereas the frequency / percentages (%) and means $\pm$ SD computed for study variables.

RESULTS: During six months study period total fifty patients with acute ischemic stroke were explored and studied. The frequency for male and female population was 32 (64%) and 18 (36%) with mean $\pm$ sd for age of male and female individuals was 58.82 ± 6.75 and 57.84 ± 8.64 respectively. gender male 30 (60%), female 20 (40%), smoking 28 (56%), alcohol 18 (36%), residence urban 35 (70%), rural 15 (30%) and the metabolic syndrome was observed in 32 (64%) patients of acute ischemic stroke.

CONCLUSION: Metabolic syndrome is more prevalent in patients with acute ischemic stroke.

KEYWORDS: Metabolic syndrome, Ischemic stroke, cerebrovascular

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Please cite this article in press Muhammad Jan Khetran et al., *Metabolic Syndrome In Patients With Acute Ischemic Stroke*, Indo Am. J. P. Sci, 2019; 06(04).

INTRODUCTION:

World Health Organization characterized stroke as quickly creating clinical indications of central or worldwide unsettling influence of cerebral capacity, enduring over 24 hours or prompting passing, with no obvious reason other than vascular starting point [1]. Stroke shows by different neurological signs and side effects relying upon degree, territory of contribution and the basic reason [2]. These incorporate unconsciousness, hemiplegia, paraplegia, monoplegia, cranial nerve paralysis, discourse unsettling influence and tangible impedance, and so forth. Of these, hemiplegia is the most widely recognized introduction, seen in about 90% of patients [3].

Metabolic disorder has pulled in colossal consideration as of late and in excess of five meanings of metabolic disorder have been proposed by different therapeutic social orders [4]. Among them new worldwide diabetes organization definition is appropriate for Pakistani populace as it gives distinctive abdomen peripheries for various ethnic gatherings [5]. Metabolic disorder is related with an expansion danger of intense ischemic stroke in older subjects with critical commitments from its individual segments. Within the sight of metabolic disorder, HDL cholesterol loses its defensive job against ischemic stroke [6]. The metabolic disorder is sadly a widespread condition and the disorder may speak to an autonomous hazard factor well beyond its segments that will require forceful conduct and perhaps pharmacologic administration adapted at turning away future stroke occasions.

PATIENT AND METHODS:

All patients with stroke age $\geq$ multi-year of age and either sex giving neuroradiological highlights of

stroke (clinically and CT examine demonstrated including major and minor stroke) were selected and entered in this cross-sectional investigation. Information gathered utilizing a pretested proforma meeting the destinations of the examination. Definite history, physical examination and fundamental examinations have been attempted. The motivation behind the examination disclosed to the patient and informative assent taken. The examination of information will be finished utilizing suitable measurable techniques. The normal blood examination alongside explicit examinations were informed while the point by point history with respect to all subjects particularly family ancestry of hypertension, diabetes mellitus, history of weight gain, liquor use and smoking. All subjects were exposed to careful physical examination which incorporated every single fringe beat including carotids to discount atherosclerosis. Examination of abdomen and hip outlines were estimated, optic fundoscopic examination for any hypertensive changes, cardiovascular, respiratory and stomach and CNS examination. No less than three pulse estimations were taken. Every one of the information was gathered on proforma and dissected in SPSS to investigate the frequencies, rates and mean $\pm$ SD.

RESULTS:

During six months study period total fifty patients with acute ischemic stroke were explored and studied. The frequency for male and female population was 32 (64%) and 18 (36%) with mean $\pm$ SD for age of male and female individuals was 58.82 ± 6.75 and 57.84 ± 8.64 respectively. The demographical and clinical profile of study population is presented in Table 1.

TABLE 1: THE DEMOGRAPHICAL AND CLINICAL PROFILE OF STUDY POPULATION

Parameter	Frequency (N=50)	Percentage (%)
AGE (yrs)		
35-39	06	12
40-49	07	14
50-59	25	50
60-69	12	24
GENDER		
Male	30	60
Female	20	40
SMOKING		
Yes	28	56
No	22	44
ALCOHOL		
Yes	18	36
No	32	64
RESIDENCE		
Urban	35	70
Rural	15	30
METABOLIC SYNDROME		
Yes	32	64
No	18	36

DISCUSSION:

Occurrence of metabolic disorder in stroke was 64% in the present investigation which is equivalent to the previous examination [7]. In the present investigation, the age occurrence of stroke with metabolic disorder was more in the middle of the age bunch 50-59 years (half). In the present investigation, guys prevailed in patients of stroke with metabolic disorder and are predictable with the previous examination [8]. In our investigation, diabetes mellitus and hypertension are essential hazard factors. Anyway, hypertension is progressively basic when contrasted with previous examinations while the diabetes mellitus was likewise is by all accounts normal. In our study, both smoking and liquor utilization contributed as autonomous hazard factors and furthermore reliable with the previous examination [9]. In our examination, the midriff circuit and triglyceride parts were increasingly normal and comparative outcomes were found in previous investigation [10]. Metabolic disorder is a bunching of hazard elements of metabolic source that are as one related with higher danger of cerebrovascular infection and henceforth the need to create systems for controlling this disorder and its segment conditions [11, 12].

CONCLUSION:

Metabolic disorder is lamentably a widespread condition that takes steps to progressively torment society and is related with an expansion hazard for intense ischemic stroke with critical commitments from its individual segments.

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